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Checklist of Iranian Aphids (Hemiptera: Stenorrhyncha: Aphidomorpha)

Fatemeh Momeni Shahraki¹, Kambiz Minaei^{1*} and Shalva Barjadze²

¹ Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture, Shiraz University, Iran.

² Institute of Zoology, Ilia State University, Giorgi Tsereteli 3, Tbilisi 0162, Georgia.

ABSTRACT. The paper presents a comprehensive compilation of 543 species and 24 subspecies of aphids, within 144 genera, belonging to 15 subfamilies, 3 families and three superfamilies of Aphidomorpha recorded to date from Iran. Among them, 35 species of aphids are endemic to Iran.

Key words: Aphids, Iran, Checklist

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Introduction

Iran forms a large part of the Iranian plateau, and covers an area of 1,623,779 km². It is bordered in the north by the Caucasus Mountains, Middle Asian natural regions and the Caspian Sea (-27 m below sea level); in the west by the Anatolian and Mesopotamian regions; in the east by the eastern part of the Iranian plateau (Afghanistan and adjacent west Pakistan) and the Baluch-Sindian region; and finally in the south by the Persian Gulf and Oman Sea, which are connected by the latter to the Indian Ocean (Zehzad et al., 2002). Aphids are herbivorous insects, which are pests of agriculture, horticulture and forestry, by sucking of the plant sap they cause direct damage to host plants by discoloration and/or deformation of leaves and shoots or producing galls and pseudo-galls. Aphids are also important vectors of

plant viral diseases (Blackman & Eastop, 2007). The known world aphid fauna consists of 5262 extant species (Favret, 2019). They are mostly found in temperate zone (Baranyovits, 1973). The aphid fauna of Iran and adjacent countries has been investigated sporradically. The first report of aphids in Iran was presented by Theobald (1920). Subsequently, Afshar (1937) refereed to some species of aphids as pests of fruit trees. But faunistic studies of Iranian aphids were initiated by Davatchi (1948). Farahbakhsh (1961), in his list of agricultural pests of Iran and Abaii (1984) reported about 50 species for trees and shrubs. Since 1970s local aphid taxonomists Hodjat and Rezwani started intensive investigation of Iranian aphid fauna. Five hundred and fifty five species have been recorded from Turkey (Akyürek et al.,

Corresponding author: Kambiz Minaei, E-mail: kminaei@gmail.com

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2019), 300 species from Pakistan (Naumann-Etienne & Remaudière, 1995), 194 species from Israel (Swirski & Amitai, 1999) and 167 species from Lebanon and Syria (Remaudière & Talhouk, 1999). In Iran 486 species are recorded (Rezwani & Radjabi, 1986; Rezwani et al. 1994; Rezwani 2010). Due to high level of endemism of vascular plants in Iran there is a high probability to find additional newly recorded species and new species for science. The aim of this paper is to provide a checklist of Iranian aphids based on available literature data for this area.

Material and methods

The geographical scope of this checklist covers the Iranian provinces and information about each species are taken from the literature. The Latin names of aphid taxa and classification are according to Favret (2019). The names of particular subgenera and taxa of lower rank within genera have been arranged in alphabetical order. Under each aphid species and subspecies the first publication from Iran is cited. Endemic aphid species are marked by asterisk. Totally, 543 species, 24 subspecies within 144 genera, belonging to 15 subfamilies, 3 families and 3 superfamilies of Aphidomorpha are presented here.

Results

So far, 543 species and 24 subspecies of aphids reported from Iran.

Order: Hemiptera (Linnaeus, 1758)

Suborder: Stenorrhyncha (Amyot & Serville, 1843)

Infraorder: Aphidomorpha (Bekker-Migdisova & Aizenberg, 1991)

Superfamily: Adelgoidea (Schouteden, 1909)

Family: Adelgidae (Annand, 1928)

Genus: *Pineus* (Shimer, 1869)

Subgenus: *Pineus* (Shimer, 1869)

1. *Pineus (Pineus) orientalis* (Dreyfus, 1888)

First record from Iran: Rezwani et al. (1994).

Superfamily: Phylloxeroidea (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854)

Family: Phylloxeridae (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854)

Subfamily: Phylloxerinae (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854)

Tribe: Acanthohermesini Börner, 1913

Genus: *Acanthohermes* Kollar, 1848

2. *Acanthohermes quercus* Kollar, 1848

First record from Iran: Rezwani et al. (1994).

Tribe: Phylloxerini (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854)

Genus: *Phylloxera* Boyer De Fonscolombe, 1834

3. *Phylloxera quercina* (Ferrari, 1872)

First record from Iran: Rezwani (2001).

Subfamily: Phylloxerinae Börner, 1908

Genus: *Phylloxera* Börner, 1908

4. *Phylloxera salicis* (Lichtenstein, 1884)

First record from Iran: Hodjat (1993).

Superfamily: Aphidoidea Latreille, 1802

Family: Aphididae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily: Eriosomatinae (Kirkaldy, 1905)

Tribe: Eriosomatini Kirkaldy, 1905

Genus: *Colopha* Monell, 1877

5. *Colopha compressa* (Koch, 1856)

First record from Iran: Hodjat (1993).

Genus: *Eriosoma* Leach, 1818

6. *Eriosoma lanigerum* (Hausmann, 1802)

First record from Iran: Afshar (1937).

7. *Eriosoma lanuginosum* (Hartig, 1839)

First record from Iran: Farahbakhsh (1961).

8. *Eriosoma ulmi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: Farahbakhsh (1961).

Genus: *Kaltenbachiella* Schouteden, 1906

9. *Kaltenbachiella pallida* (Haliday, 1838)

First record from Iran: Hodjat (1993).

Genus: *Tetraneura* Hartig, 1841

Subgenus: *Tetraneura* Hartig, 1841

10. *Tetraneura (Tetraneura) africana* Van Der Goot, 1912

First record from Iran: Eastop & Hodjat (1980).

11. *Tetraneura* (*Tetraneura*) *caerulescens* (Passerini, 1856)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

12. *Tetraneura* (*Tetraneura*) *ulmi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Subgenus: *Tetraneurella* Hille Ris Lambers, 1970

13. *Tetraneura* (*Tetraneurella*) *nigriabdominalis* (Sasaki, 1899)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Synonym: *Tetraneura* (*Tetraneurella*) *akinire* (Sasaki, 1905).

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

Tribe: Fordini Baker, 1920

Genus: *Aploneura* Passerini, 1863

14. *Aploneura* *lentisci* (Passerini, 1856)

First record from Iran: [Taghizadeh & Safavi \(1960\)](#).

Genus: *Asiphonella* Theobald, 1923

15. *Asiphonella* *cynodonti* (Das, 1918)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

16. *Asiphonella* *dactylonii* Theobald, 1923

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

Genus: *Baizongia* Rondani, 1848

17. *Baizongia* *pistaciae* (Linnaeus, 1767)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

Genus: *Forda* von Heyden, 1837

18. *Forda* *formicaria* von Heyden, 1837

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1954\)](#).

19. *Forda* *hirsuta* (Mordvilko, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

20. *Forda* *kaussarii* Davatchi & Remaudière, 1957*

First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1957\)](#).

21. *Forda* *marginata* Koch, 1857

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

22. *Forda* *orientalis* George, 1928

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

23. *Forda* *riccobonii* (Stefani, 1899)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Genus: *Geoica* Hart, 1894

24. *Geoica* *setulosa* (Passerini, 1860)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

25. *Geoica* *utricularia* (Passerini, 1856)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1954\)](#).

26. *Geoica* *utricularia muticae* (Mordvilko, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

Genus: *Paracletus* von Heyden, 1837

27. *Paracletus* *cimiciformis* von Heyden, 1837

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

Genus: *Rectinasus* Theobald, 1914

28. *Rectinasus* *buxtoni* Theobald, 1914

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Slavum* Mordvilko, 1927

29. *Slavum* *esfandiarii* Davatchi & Remaudière, 1957

First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1957\)](#).

30. *Slavum* *lentiscoides* Mordvilko, 1927

First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1957\)](#).

31. *Slavum* *mordvilko*i Kreutzberg, 1953

First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1957\)](#).

32. *Slavum* *wertheimae* Hille Ris Lambers, 1957

First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1957\)](#).

Genus: *Smynthuroides* Westwood, 1849

33. *Smynthuroides* *betae* Westwood, 1849

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

Tribe: Pemphigini Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854

Genus: *Pemphigus* Hartig, 1839

Subgenus: *Pemphiginus* Börner, 1930

34. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphiginus*) *populi* Courchet, 1881

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

35. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphiginus*) *vesicarius* Passerini, 1861

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

Subgenus: Pemphigus Hartig, 1839

36. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *borealis* Tullgren, 1909

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

37. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *bursarius* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

38. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *fuscicornis* (Koch, 1857)

First record from Iran: [Derakhshan Shadmehri \(1994\)](#).

39. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *immunis* Buckton, 1896

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

40. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *passeki* Börner, 1952

First record from Iran: [Najmi et al. \(2018\)](#).

41. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *populinigræ* (Schrank, 1801)

First record from Iran: [Najmi et al. \(2018\)](#).

42. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *protospiræ* Lichtenstein, 1884

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

43. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *saliciradicis* (Börner, 1950)

First record from Iran: [Barjadze \(2009\)](#).

44. *Pemphigus* (*Pemphigus*) *spyrothecæ* Passerini, 1856

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

Genus: Prociphilus Koch, 1857**Subgenus: Prociphilus Koch, 1857**

45. *Prociphilus* (*Prociphilus*) *fraxini* (Fabricius, 1777)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Subgenus: Meliarhizophagus Smith, 1974

46. *Prociphilus* (*Meliarhizophagus*) *fraxinifolii* (Riley, 1879)

First record from Iran: [Tajmiri et al. \(2016\)](#).

Genus: Thecabius Koch, 1857**Subgenus: Thecabius Koch, 1857**

47. *Thecabius* (*Thecabius*) *affinis* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Subfamily: Phloeomyzinae Mordvilko, 1934**Genus: Phloeomyzus de Horváth, 1896**

48. *Phloeomyzus passerinii* (Signoret, 1875)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

Subfamily: Anoeciinae Tullgren, 1909**Genus: Anoecia Koch, 1857****Subgenus: Anoecia Koch, 1857**

49. *Anoecia* (*Anoecia*) *corni* (Fabricius, 1775)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1954\)](#).

50. *Anoecia* (*Anoecia*) *vagans* (Koch, 1856)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

51. *Anoecia* (*Anoecia*) *zirnitsi* Mordvilko, 1931

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

Subfamily: Thelaxinae Baker, 1920**Genus: Thelaxes Westwood, 1840**

52. *Thelaxes dryophila* (Schrank, 1801)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

53. *Thelaxes suberi* (Del Guercio, 1911)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Subfamily: Mindarinae Tullgren, 1909**Genus: Mindarus Koch, 1857**

54. *Mindarus abietinus* Koch, 1857

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subfamily: Drepanosiphinae Herrich-Schaeffer, 1857**Genus: Drepanosiphoniella Davatchi, Hille Ris Lambers & Remaudière, 1957**

55. *Drepanosiphoniella aceris* Davatchi, Hille Ris Lambers & Remaudière, 1957

First record from Iran: [Davatchi et al. \(1957\)](#).

Genus: Drepanosiphum Koch, 1855

56. *Drepanosiphum acerinum* (Walker, 1848)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

57. *Drepanosiphum iranicum* Hille Ris Lambers, 1971*

First record from Iran: [Hille Ris Lambers \(1971\)](#).

58. *Drepanosiphum oregonensis* Granovsky, 1939

First record from Iran: [Hille Ris Lambers \(1971\)](#).

59. *Drepanosiphum platanoidis* (Schrank, 1801)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Subfamily: Phyllaphidinae Herrich-Schaeffer, 1857

Genus: Phyllaphis Koch, 1856

60. *Phyllaphis fagi* (Linnaeus, 1761)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).

Subfamily: Calaphidinae Oestlund, 1919

Tribe: Calaphidini Oestlund, 1919

Genus: Betulaphis Glendenning, 1926

61. *Betulaphis quadrituberculata* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Tribe: Panaphidini Oestlund, 1923

Genus: Appendiseta Richards, 1965

62. *Appendiseta robiniae* (Gillette, 1907)
First record from Iran: [Entezari et al. \(2016\)](#).

Genus: Bicaudella Rusanova, 1943

63. *Bicaudella astragalensis* (Rusanova, 1943)
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

64. *Bicaudella denaensis* (Remaudière, 1989)*
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

65. *Bicaudella farsiana* (Remaudière, 1989)*
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

66. *Bicaudella laurestanica* (Remaudière, 1989)*
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

67. *Bicaudella rostrata* (Remaudière, 1989)*
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

Genus: Chromaphis Walker, 1870

68. *Chromaphis juglandicola* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Genus: Eucallipterus Schouteden, 1906

69. *Eucallipterus tiliae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
First record from Iran: [Afshar \(1937\)](#).

Genus: Hoplocallis Pintera, 1952

70. *Hoplocallis picta* (Ferrari, 1872)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: Hoplochaetaphis Aizenberg, 1959

71. *Hoplochaetaphis zachvatkini* (Aizenberg & Moravskaya, 1959)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: Myzocallis Passerini, 1860

Subgenus: Agrioaphis Walker, 1870

72. *Myzocallis (Agrioaphis) castanicola* Baker, 1917
First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Subgenus: Myzocallis Passerini, 1860

73. *Myzocallis (Myzocallis) boernerii* Stroyan, 1957

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

74. *Myzocallis (Myzocallis) carpini* (Koch, 1855)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

75. *Myzocallis (Myzocallis) coryli* (Goeze, 1788)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).

Subgenus: Pasekia Aizenberg, 1959

76. *Myzocallis (Pasekia) komareki* (Pašek, 1953)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

77. *Myzocallis (Pasekia) persica* Quednau & Remaudière, 1994

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: Panaphis Kirkaldy, 1904

78. *Panaphis juglandis* (Goeze, 1778)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Genus: Pterocallis Passerini, 1860

Subgenus: Pterocallis Passerini, 1860

79. *Pterocallis (Pterocallis) alni* (De Geer, 1773)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

80. *Pterocallis (Pterocallis) maculata* (von Heyden, 1837)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Shivaphis Das, 1918

Subgenus: Shivaphis Das, 1918

81. *Shivaphis (Shivaphis) celti* Das, 1918
First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Genus: *Therioaphis* Walker, 1870**Subgenus: *Pterocallidium* Börner, 1949**

82. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *azerbaidjanica* Remaudière, 1989*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

83. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *kermanica* Remaudière, 1989*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

84. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *khayami* Remaudière, 1989

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

85. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *trifolii* (Monell, 1882)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

86. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *trifolii maculatus* (Buckton, 1899)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

87. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *trifolii trifolii* (Monell, 1882)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

88. *Therioaphis* (*Pterocallidium*) *trifolii ventromaculata* Müller, 1968

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2001\)](#).

Subgenus: *Rhizoberlesia* Del Guercio, 1915

89. *Therioaphis* (*Rhizoberlesia*) *arnaultae* Remaudière, 1989

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

90. *Therioaphis* (*Rhizoberlesia*) *brachytricha* Hille Ris Lambers & van den Bosch, 1964

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

91. *Therioaphis* (*Rhizoberlesia*) *riehmi* (Börner, 1949)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Subgenus: *Therioaphis* Walker, 1870

92. *Therioaphis* (*Therioaphis*) *astragali* (Dzhibladze, 1959)

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

93. *Therioaphis* (*Therioaphis*) *litoralis* Hille Ris Lambers & van den Bosch, 1964

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

94. *Therioaphis* (*Therioaphis*) *loti* Hille Ris Lambers & van den Bosch, 1964

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

95. *Therioaphis* (*Therioaphis*) *natricis* Hille Ris Lambers & van den Bosch, 1964

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

96. *Therioaphis* (*Therioaphis*) *ononidis* (Kaltenbach, 1846)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: *Tinocallis* Matsumura, 1919**Subgenus: *Eotinocallis* Quednau, 2003**

97. *Tinocallis* (*Eotinocallis*) *platani* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

98. *Tinocallis* (*Eotinocallis*) *zelkovae* Dzhibladze, 1957

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Subgenus: *Sappocallis* Matsumura, 1919

99. *Tinocallis* (*Sappocallis*) *nevskyi* Remaudière, Quednau & Heie, 1988

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

100. *Tinocallis* (*Sappocallis*) *saltans* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).

Genus: *Sarucallis* Shinji, 1922

101. *Sarucallis* *kahawaluokalani* (Kirkaldy, 1907)

First record from Iran: [Gholamzadeh-Chitgar \(2017\)](#).

Genus: *Tuberculatus* Mordvilko, 1894**Subgenus: *Tuberculatus* Mordvilko, 1894**

102. *Tuberculatus* (*Tuberculatus*) *querceus* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Subgenus: *Tuberculoides* van der Goot, 1915

103. *Tuberculatus* (*Tuberculoides*) *annulatus* (Hartig, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

104. *Tuberculatus* (*Tuberculoides*) *maximus* Hille Ris Lambers, 1974

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Subfamily: *Saltusaphidinae* Baker, 1920**Tribe: *Saltusaphidini* Baker, 1920**

Genus: *Iziphya* Nevsky, 1929**105.** *Iziphya bufo* (Walker, 1848)First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1998\)](#).Synonym: *Iziphya austriaca* (Boerner, 1950)**Genus: *Saltusaphis* Theobald, 1915****106.** *Saltusaphis scirpus* Theobald, 1915First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).**Tribe: Thripsaphidini Börner, 1949****Genus: *Subsaltusaphis* Quednau, 1953****Subgenus: *Subsaltusaphis* Quednau, 1954****107.** *Subsaltusaphis* (*Subsaltusaphis*) *ornata* (Theobald, 1927)First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).**Subfamily: Chaitophorinae Mordvilko, 1908****Tribe: Chaitophorini Mordvilko, 1908****Genus: *Chaitophorus* Koch, 1854****108.** *Chaitophorus capreae* (Mosley, 1841)First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).**109.** *Chaitophorus euphraticus* Hodjat, 1981First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**110.** *Chaitophorus hillerislambersi* Pintera, 1987First record from Iran: [Mortazavi et al. \(2015\)](#).**111.** *Chaitophorus israeliticus* Hille Ris Lambers, 1960First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**112.** *Chaitophorus leucomelas* Koch, 1854First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).**113.** *Chaitophorus melanosiphon* Pintera, 1987First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).**114.** *Chaitophorus nigra* (Oestlund, 1886)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**115.** *Chaitophorus nigrinus* Hille Ris Lambers, 1966First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).**116.** *Chaitophorus pakistanicus* Hille Ris Lambers, 1966First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).**117.** *Chaitophorus populeti* (Panzer, 1801)First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).**118.** *Chaitophorus populialbae* (Boyer De Fonscolombe, 1841)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**119.** *Chaitophorus remaudierei* Pintera, 1987*First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).**120.** *Chaitophorus salicti* (Schrank, 1801)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**121.** *Chaitophorus salijaponicus* Essig & Kuwana, 1918First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**122.** *Chaitophorus salijaponicus niger* Mordvilko, 1929First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**123.** *Chaitophorus truncatus* (Hausmann, 1802)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).**124.** *Chaitophorus vitellinae* (Schrank, 1801)First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).**Genus: *Lambersaphis* Narzikulov, 1961****125.** *Lambersaphis pruinosa* (Narzikulov 1954)First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2004\)](#).**Genus: *Periphyllus* van der Hoeven, 1863****126.** *Periphyllus acericola* (Walker, 1848)First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).**127.** *Periphyllus aceris* (Linnaeus, 1761)First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).**128.** *Periphyllus bulgaricus* Tashev, 1964First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).**129.** *Periphyllus lyropictus* (Kessler, 1886)First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).**130.** *Periphyllus obscurus* Mamontova, 1955First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).**131.** *Periphyllus testudinaceus* (Ferne, 1852)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).**Tribe: Siphini Mordvilko, 1928****Genus: *Atheroides* Haliday, 1839****132.** *Atheroides serrulatus* Haliday, 1839First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).**Genus: *Chaetosiphella* Hille Ris Lambers, 1939****133.** *Chaetosiphella longirostris* Wieczorek, 2008

First record from Iran: [Mosapour et al. \(2019\)](#).

134. *Chaetosiphella stipae* Hille Ris Lambers, 1947

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Laingia* Theobald, 1922

135. *Laingia psammae* Theobald, 1922

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1981\)](#).

Genus: *Sipha* Passerini, 1860

Subgenus: *Sipha* Passerini, 1860

136. *Sipha (Sipha) flava* (Forbes, 1885)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

137. *Sipha (Sipha) glyceriae* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

Subgenus: *Rungisia* Mimeur, 1933

138. *Sipha (Rungisia) elegans* (Del Guercio, 1905)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Synonym: *Sipha kurdjumovi* Mordvilko, 1921

139. *Sipha (Rungisia) maydis* Passerini, 1860

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

Subfamily: Aphidinae Latreille, 1802

Tribe: Aphidini Latreille, 1802

Genus: *Aphis* Linnaeus, 1758

Subgenus: *Aphis* Linnaeus, 1758

140. *Aphis (Aphis) acetosae* Linnaeus, 1767

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

141. *Aphis (Aphis) affinis* Del Guercio, 1911

First record from Iran: [Tuatay & Remaudière \(1964\)](#).

142. *Aphis (Aphis) althaeae* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Synonym: *Aphis dawletshinae* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1966)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

143. *Aphis (Aphis) ballotae* Passerini, 1860

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Synonym: *Aphis (Aphis) balloticola* (Szelegiewicz, 1968)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

144. *Aphis (Aphis) brachysiphon* Narzikulov, 1964

First record from Iran: [Blackman & Eastop \(2006\)](#).

145. *Aphis (Aphis) brohmeri* Börner, 1952

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

146. *Aphis (Aphis) brotericola* Mier Durante, 1978

First record from Iran: [Barjadze et al. \(2017\)](#).

147. *Aphis (Aphis) catalpae* Mamontova, 1953

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

148. *Aphis (Aphis) chloris* Koch, 1854

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

149. *Aphis (Aphis) ciceri* Müller, 1986

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

150. *Aphis (Aphis) confusa* Walker, 1849

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

151. *Aphis (Aphis) craccae* Linnaeus, 1758

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

152. *Aphis (Aphis) craccivora* Koch, 1854

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

153. *Aphis (Aphis) crepidis* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Starý et al. \(2000\)](#).

154. *Aphis (Aphis) cytisorum* Hartig, 1841

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

155. *Aphis (Aphis) dlabolai* Holman, 1992*

First record from Iran: [Holman \(1992\)](#).

156. *Aphis (Aphis) euphorbiae* Kaltenbach, 1843

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

157. *Aphis (Aphis) euphorbicola* Rezwani & Lampel, 1990*

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Lampel \(1990\)](#).

158. *Aphis (Aphis) fabae* Scopoli, 1763

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

159. *Aphis (Aphis) fabae cirsiancthooidis* Scopoli, 1763

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

160. *Aphis (Aphis) fabae evonymi* Fabricius, 1775
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
161. *Aphis (Aphis) fabae fabae* Scopoli, 1763
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).
162. *Aphis (Aphis) frangulae* Kaltenbach, 1845
First record from Iran: [Afshar \(1937\)](#).
163. *Aphis (Aphis) frangulae frangulae* Kaltenbach, 1845
First record from Iran: [Afshar, \(1937\)](#).
164. *Aphis (Aphis) frangulae testacea* Thomas, 1968
First record from Iran: [Samii \(1992\)](#).
165. *Aphis (Aphis) farinosa* Gmelin, 1790
First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).
166. *Aphis (Aphis) forbesi* Weed, 1889
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).
167. *Aphis (Aphis) galiiscabri* Schrank, 1801
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).
168. *Aphis (Aphis) gerardiana* Mordvilko, 1929
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).
169. *Aphis (Aphis) gossypii* Glover, 1877
First record from Iran: [Afshar \(1937\)](#).
170. *Aphis (Aphis) hederiae* Kaltenbach, 1843
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).
171. *Aphis (Aphis) hispanica* Hille Ris Lambers, 1959
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
172. *Aphis (Aphis) idaei* van der Goot, 1912
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).
173. *Aphis (Aphis) illinoisensis* Shimer, 1866
First record from Iran: [Heidarnia & Derakhshan \(2018\)](#).
174. *Aphis (Aphis) intybi* Koch, 1855
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).
175. *Aphis (Aphis) kachkoulii* Remaudière, 1989
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).
176. *Aphis (Aphis) lambersi* (Börner, 1940)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
177. *Aphis (Aphis) loti* Kaltenbach, 1862
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
178. *Aphis (Aphis) myrsinitidis* Petrović-Obradović & Leclant, 1998
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
179. *Aphis (Aphis) nasturtii* Kaltenbach, 1843
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).
180. *Aphis (Aphis) nepetae* Kaltenbach, 1843
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
181. *Aphis (Aphis) nerii* Boyer de Fonscolombe, 1841
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).
182. *Aphis (Aphis) origani* Passerini, 1860
First record from Iran: [Starý et al. \(2000\)](#).
183. *Aphis (Aphis) parietariae* Theobald, 1922
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
184. *Aphis (Aphis) picridis* (Börner, 1950)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
185. *Aphis (Aphis) plantaginis* Goeze, 1778
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
186. *Aphis (Aphis) polygonata* (Nevsky, 1929)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).
Synonym: *Aphis avicularis* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1931)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).
187. *Aphis (Aphis) pomi* De Geer, 1773
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).
188. *Aphis (Aphis) potentillae* Nevsky, 1929
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
189. *Aphis (Aphis) praeterita* Walker, 1849
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
190. *Aphis (Aphis) propinqua* Holman, 1992*
First record from Iran: [Holman \(1992\)](#).
191. *Aphis (Aphis) pseudopulchella* (Blanchard & Everard Eel, 1944)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
192. *Aphis (Aphis) punicae* Passerini, 1863
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).
193. *Aphis (Aphis) roepkei* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1931)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

194. *Aphis (Aphis) ruborum* (Börner & Schilder, 1931)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

195. *Aphis (Aphis) rumicis* Linnaeus, 1758

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

196. *Aphis (Aphis) salicariae* Koch, 1855

First record from Iran: [Mortazavi et al. \(2015\)](#).

Synonym: *corniella* Hille Ris Lambers, 1935

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

197. *Aphis (Aphis) salsolae* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

198. *Aphis (Aphis) salviae* Walker, 1852

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

199. *Aphis (Aphis) sambuci* Linnaeus, 1758

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

200. *Aphis (Aphis) sanguisorbae* Schrank, 1801

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

201. *Aphis (Aphis) sanguisorbae poterii* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

202. *Aphis (Aphis) sedi* Kaltenbach, 1843

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

203. *Aphis (Aphis) solanella* Theobald, 1914

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

204. *Aphis (Aphis) spiraecola* Patch, 1914

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1982\)](#).

Synonym: *Aphis (Aphis) citricola* (van der Goot, 1912)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Eastop \(1982\)](#).

205. *Aphis (Aphis) spiraephaga* Müller, 1961

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

206. *Aphis (Aphis) stachydis* Mordvilko, 1929

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

207. *Aphis (Aphis) taraxacicola* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

208. *Aphis (Aphis) teucrii* (Börner, 1942)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

209. *Aphis (Aphis) thalictri* Koch, 1854

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

210. *Aphis (Aphis) umbrella* (Börner, 1950)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

211. *Aphis (Aphis) urticata* Gmelin, 1790

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

212. *Aphis (Aphis) verbasci* Schrank, 1801

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

213. *Aphis (Aphis) viticis* Ferrari, 1872

First record from Iran: [Tuatay & Remaudière \(1964\)](#).

Subgenus: Bursaphis Baker, 1934

214. *Aphis (Bursaphis) epilobii* Kaltenbach, 1843

First record from Iran: [Samii \(1992\)](#).

215. *Aphis (Bursaphis) grossulariae* Kaltenbach, 1843

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: Pseudoprotaphis Kadyrbekov, 2001

216. *Aphis (Pseudoprotaphis) erigerontis* Holman, 1966

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Subgenus: Toxoptera Koch, 1856

217. *Aphis (Toxoptera) aurantii* Boyer de Fonscolombe, 1841

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1983\)](#).

Genus: Toxopterina Börner, 1940

218. *Toxopterina vandergooti* (Börner, 1933)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Brachyunguis Das, 1918

Subgenus: Brachyunguis Das, 1918

219. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) cuscutae* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

220. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) cynanchi* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

221. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) harmalae* Das, 1918

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Radjabi \(1986\)](#).

222. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) kaussarii* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1955*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1955\)](#).

223. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) nevskyi* (Kreutzberg, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

224. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) skafi* Remaudière & Talhouk, 2001

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

225. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) tamaricis* (Lichtenstein, 1886)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

226. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) tamaricophilus* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

227. *Brachyunguis (Brachyunguis) zygophylli* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Subgenus: Xerophilaphis Nevsky, 1928

228. *Brachyunguis (Xerophilaphis) saxaulica* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: Brevicorynella Nevsky, 1928

229. *Brevicorynella quadrimaculata* Nevsky, 1928

First record from Iran: [Barkhordari et al. \(1981\)](#).

Genus: Ephedraphis Hille Ris Lambers, 1959

230. *Ephedraphis ephedrae* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Genus: Hyalopterus Koch, 1854

231. *Hyalopterus amygdali* (Blanchard, 1840)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

232. *Hyalopterus arundiformis* Ghulamullah, 1942

First record from Iran: [Sarani \(2015\)](#).

Synonym: *Hyalopterus persikonus* Miller, Lozier & Foottit, 2008

First record from Iran: [Sarani \(2015\)](#).

233. *Hyalopterus pruni* (Geoffroy, 1762)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

Genus: Hysteroneura Davis, 1919

234. *Hysteroneura setariae* (Thomas, 1878)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Melanaphis van der Goot, 1917

235. *Melanaphis donacis* (Passerini, 1861)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

236. *Melanaphis pyraria* (Passerini, 1861)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Radjabi \(1986\)](#).

237. *Melanaphis sacchari* (Zehntner, 1897)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Genus: Protaphis Börner, 1952

238. *Protaphis alexandrae* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

239. *Protaphis anthemidis* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

240. *Protaphis anuraphoides* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

241. *Protaphis carthami* (Das, 1918)

First record from Iran: [Blackman & Eastop \(2006\)](#).

242. *Protaphis elatior* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

243. *Protaphis elongata* (Nevsky 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

244. *Protaphis pseudocardui* (Theobald, 1915)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

245. *Protaphis terricola* (Rondani, 1847)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

Genus: Rhopalosiphum Koch, 1854

246. *Rhopalosiphum maidis* (Fitch, 1856)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

247. *Rhopalosiphum musae* (Schouteden, 1906)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984b\)](#).

248. *Rhopalosiphum nymphaeae* (Linnaeus, 1761)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

249. *Rhopalosiphum oxyacanthae* (Schrank, 1801)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984b\)](#).

Synonym: *Rhopalosiphum insertum* Walker, 1849

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984b\)](#).

250. *Rhopalosiphum padi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

251. *Rhopalosiphum rufiabdominale* (Sasaki, 1899)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Schizaphis* Börner, 1931

Subgenus: *Paraschizaphis* Hille Ris Lambers, 1947

252. *Schizaphis* (*Paraschizaphis*) *caricis* (Schouteden, 1906)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984b\)](#).

253. *Schizaphis* (*Paraschizaphis*) *scirpi* (Passerini, 1874)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984b\)](#).

Subgenus: *Schizaphis* Börner, 1931

254. *Schizaphis* (*Schizaphis*) *graminum* (Rondani, 1852)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1954\)](#).

255. *Schizaphis* (*Schizaphis*) *minuta* (van der Goot, 1917)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

256. *Schizaphis* (*Schizaphis*) *nigerrima* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1931)

First record from Iran: [Mortazavi et al. \(2015\)](#).

257. *Schizaphis* (*Schizaphis*) *rotundiventris* (Signoret, 1860)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

258. *Schizaphis* (*Schizaphis*) *rufula* Walker, 1849

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Swirskiaphis* Hille Ris Lambers, 1966

259. *Swirskiaphis polychaeta* Hille Ris Lambers, 1966

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Xerobion* Nevsky, 1928

260. *Xerobion album* (Remaudiere & Davatchi, 1959)

First record from Iran: [Remaudiere & Davatchi \(1959b\)](#).

261. *Xerobion cinae* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

262. *Xerobion eriosomatium* Nevsky, 1928

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Tribe: *Macrosiphini* Wilson, 1910

Genus: *Acaudinum* Börner, 1930

Subgenus: *Protacaudinum* Holman, 1991

263. *Acaudinum* (*Protacaudinum*) *beheni* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1959

First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1959b\)](#).

Genus: *Acyrtosiphon* Mordvilko, 1914

Subgenus: *Acyrtosiphon* Mordvilko, 1914

264. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *bidentis* (Eastop, 1953)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

265. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *cyparissiae* (Koch, 1855)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

266. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *daphnidis* Ilharco, 1996

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

267. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *gossypii* Mordvilko, 1914

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

268. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *ignotum* Mordvilko, 1914

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

269. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *ilka* Mordvilko, 1914

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

270. *Acyrtosiphon* (*Acyrtosiphon*) *kondoi* Shinji, 1938

First record from Iran: [Monajemi & Esmaili \(1981\)](#).

271. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) lactucae* (Passerini, 1860)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

272. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) loti* (Theobald, 1913)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

273. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) malvae* (Mosley, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

274. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) malvae agrimoniae* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

275. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) malvae malvae* (Mosley, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Synonym: *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) malvae geranii* (Kaltenbach, 1862)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

276. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) malvae poterii* Prior & Stroyan, 1964

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

277. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) pisum* (Harris, 1776)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

278. *Acyrtosiphon (Acyrtosiphon) scariolae* Nevsky, 1929

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Subgenus: *Xanthomyzus* Narzikulov, 1966

279. *Acyrtosiphon (Xanthomyzus) lambersi* Leclant & Remaudière 1974

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: *Allocotaphis* Börner, 1950

280. *Allocotaphis quaestionis* (Börner, 1942)

First record from Iran: [Darsouei et al. \(2011\)](#).

Genus: *Amegosiphon* Narzukulov, 1958

281. *Amegosiphon platicaudum* (Narzukulov, 1953)

First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1959a\)](#).

Synonym: *Elbourzaphis behboudii* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1959

First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1959a\)](#).

Genus: *Ammiaphis* Börner, 1952

282. *Ammiaphis sii* (Koch, 1855)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Amphorophora* Buckton, 1876

Subgenus: *Amphorophora* Buckton, 1876

283. *Amphorophora (Amphorophora) catharinae* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

284. *Amphorophora (Amphorophora) rubi* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: *Anuraphis* Del Guercio, 1907

285. *Anuraphis cachryos* Barbagallo & Stroyan, 1982

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

286. *Anuraphis catonii* Hille Ris Lambers, 1935

First record from Iran: [Derakhshan Shadmehri \(1994\)](#).

287. *Anuraphis farfarae* (Koch, 1854)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

288. *Anuraphis subterranea* (Walker, 1852)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Aphidura* Hille Ris Lambers, 1956

289. *Aphidura acanthophylli* Remaudière, 1989*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

290. *Aphidura bozhkoe* (Narzikulov, 1958)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2004\)](#).

291. *Aphidura gypsophilae* Mamontova, 1963

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

292. *Aphidura ornata* Hille Ris Lambers, 1956

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1998\)](#).

293. *Aphidura ornatella* Narzikulov & Winkler, 1960

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

294. *Aphidura pakistanensis* Nieto Nafria, Mier Durante & Remaudière, 2013

First record from Iran: [Barjadze et al. \(2017\)](#).

295. *Aphidura picta* Hille Ris Lambers, 1956

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

296. *Aphidura togaica* Kadyrbekov, 2013
First record from Iran: [Barjadze et al. \(2017\)](#).

Genus: *Aspidaphis* (Gillette, 1917)

297. *Aspidaphis adjuvans* (Walker, 1848)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Genus: *Aulacorthum* Mordvilko, 1914

Subgenus: *Aulacorthum* Mordvilko, 1914

298. *Aulacorthum* (*Aulacorthum*) *palustre*
Hille Ris Lambers, 1947
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

299. *Aulacorthum* (*Aulacorthum*) *solani*
(Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

300. *Aulacorthum* (*Aulacorthum*) *speyeri*
Börner, 1939
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: *Brachycaudus* van der Goot, 1913

Subgenus: *Acaudus* van der Goot, 1913

301. *Brachycaudus* (*Acaudus*) *cerasicola*
(Mordvilko, 1929)
First record from Iran: [Sedighi et al. \(2018\)](#).

302. *Brachycaudus* (*Acaudus*) *divaricata*
Shaposhnikov, 1956
First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1953\)](#).

303. *Brachycaudus* (*Acaudus*) *iranicus*
Davatchi & Remaudière, 1953
First record from Iran: [Davatchi & Remaudière \(1953\)](#).

304. *Brachycaudus* (*Acaudus*) *lateralis*
(Walker, 1848)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Lampel \(1990\)](#).

305. *Brachycaudus* (*Acaudus*) *lychnidis*
(Linnaeus, 1758)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: *Appelia* Börner, 1930

306. *Brachycaudus* (*Appelia*) *prunicola*
(Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Radjabi \(1986\)](#).

307. *Brachycaudus* (*Appelia*) *schwartzi*
(Börner, 1931)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

308. *Brachycaudus* (*Appelia*) *tragopogonis*
(Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

309. *Brachycaudus* (*Appelia*) *tragopogonis*
setosus (Hille Ris Lambers, 1948)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Subgenus: *Brachycaudus* van der Goot, 1913

310. *Brachycaudus* (*Brachycaudus*) *helichrysi*
(Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).
Synonym: *Aphis verbenae* Macchiati, 1883
First record from Iran: [Rajabi-Mazhar et al. \(2010\)](#).

311. *Brachycaudus* (*Brachycaudus*) *salicinae*
Börner, 1939
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

312. *Brachycaudus* (*Brachycaudus*) *spiraeae*
Börner, 1932
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Subgenus: *Mordvilkomemor* Shaposhnikov, 1950

313. *Brachycaudus* (*Mordvilkomemor*) *pilosus*
(Mordvilko, 1929)
First record from Iran: [Noorbakhsh et al. \(2005\)](#).

Subgenus: *Nevskyaphis* Shaposhnikov, 1950

314. *Brachycaudus* (*Nevskyaphis*) *ballotae*
Passerini, 1860
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

315. *Brachycaudus* (*Nevskyaphis*) *bicolor*
(Nevsky, 1929)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: *Prunaphis* Shaposhnikov, 1964

316. *Brachycaudus* (*Prunaphis*) *cardui*
(Linnaeus, 1758)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Subgenus: *Scrophulaphis* Andreev, 1982

317. *Brachycaudus (Scrophulaphis) persicae* (Passerini, 1860)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Synonym: *Brachycaudus (Scrophulaphis) persicaecola* Boisduval, 1867

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Subgenus: *Thuleaphis* Hille Ris Lambers, 1960

318. *Brachycaudus (Thuleaphis) amygdalinus* (Schouteden, 1905)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

319. *Brachycaudus (Thuleaphis) rumexicolens* (Patch, 1917)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Brachycorynella* Aizenberg, 1956

320. *Brachycorynella asparagi* (Mordvilko, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

321. *Brachycorynella lonicerina* (Shaposhnikov, 1952)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Brevicoryne* Das, 1915

322. *Brevicoryne brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Afshar \(1937\)](#).

323. *Brevicoryne crambe* Bozhko, 1950

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Synonym: *Brevicoryne crambinistataricae* (Bozhko, 1953)

324. *Brevicoryne nigrisiphunculata* Hodjat, 1981

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Genus: *Capitophorus* van der Goot, 1913

325. *Capitophorus carduinus* (Walker, 1850)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1998\)](#).

326. *Capitophorus elaeagni* (Del Guercio, 1894)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

327. *Capitophorus hippophaes* (Walker, 1852)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

328. *Capitophorus horni* Börner, 1931

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1998\)](#).

329. *Capitophorus inulae* (Passerini, 1860)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

330. *Capitophorus similis* van der Goot, 1915

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

331. *Capitophorus wojciechowskii* Wieczorek & Kanturski, 2015*

First record from Iran: [Wieczorek & Kanturski \(2015\)](#).

Genus: *Cavariella* Del Guercio, 1911

Subgenus: *Cavariella* Heinze, 1960

332. *Cavariella (Cavariella) aquatica* (Gillette & Bragg, 1916)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

Synonym: *Cavariella hillerislambersi* Ossiannilsson, 1959

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

Subgenus: *Cavariella* Del Guercio, 1911

333. *Cavariella (Cavariella) aegopodii* (Scopoli, 1763)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Mossadegh \(1979\)](#).

334. *Cavariella (Cavariella) archangelicae* (Scopoli, 1763)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

335. *Cavariella (Cavariella) aspidaphoides* Hille Ris Lambers, 1969

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

336. *Cavariella (Cavariella) cicutae* (Koch, 1854)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

337. *Cavariella (Cavariella) pastinacae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

338. *Cavariella (Cavariella) salicicola* (Matsumura, 1917)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

339. *Cavariella (Cavariella) theobaldi* (Gillette & Bragg, 1918)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

Genus: *Ceruraphis* Börner, 1926

340. *Ceruraphis eriophori* (Walker, 1848)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Chaetosiphon* Mordvilko, 1914

Subgenus: *Chaetosiphon* Mordvilko, 1914

341. *Chaetosiphon* (*Chaetosiphon*) *chaetosiphon* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: *Pentatrachopus* Börner, 1930

342. *Chaetosiphon* (*Pentatrachopus*) *tetrarhodum* (Walker, 1849)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Chaitaphis* Nevsky, 1928

343. *Chaitaphis safavii* Remaudière, 1989*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

344. *Chaitaphis tenuicauda* Nevsky, 1928

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

Genus: *Chondrillobium* Bozhko, 1961

345. *Chondrillobium blattnyi* (Pintera, 1959)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Clypeoaphis* Soliman, 1938

346. *Clypeoaphis suaedae* (Mimeur, 1934)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Genus: *Coloradoa* Wilson, 1910

347. *Coloradoa absinthiella* (Ossianniellsson, 1962)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

348. *Coloradoa absinthii* (Lichtenstein, 1886)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

349. *Coloradoa abrotani* (Koch, 1854)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

350. *Coloradoa achilleae* Hille Ris Lambers, 1939

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

351. *Coloradoa artemisiae* (del Guercio, 1914)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

352. *Coloradoa heinzei* (Börner, 1952)

First record from Iran: [Mehrparvar & Rezwani \(2007\)](#).

353. *Coloradoa rufomaculata* (Wilson, 1908)

First record from Iran: [Naumann-Etienne & Remaudière \(1995\)](#).

354. *Coloradoa santolinae* Hille Ris Lambers, 1948*

First record from Iran: [Stary et al. \(2000\)](#).

355. *Coloradoa viridis* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Corylobium* Mordvilko, 1914

356. *Corylobium avellanae* (Schrank, 1801)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Genus: *Cryptomyzus* Oestlund, 1923

Subgenus: *Cryptomyzus* Oestlund, 1923

357. *Cryptomyzus* (*Cryptomyzus*) *ballotae* Hille Ris Lambers, 1953

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

358. *Cryptomyzus* (*Cryptomyzus*) *behboudii* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1961

First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1961\)](#).

359. *Cryptomyzus* (*Cryptomyzus*) *korschelti* Börner, 1938

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Cryptosiphum* Buckton, 1879

360. *Cryptosiphum artemisiae* (Buckton, 1879)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Genus: *Davatchiaphis* Remaudière, 1964

361. *Davatchiaphis persica* Remaudière, 1964*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1964\)](#).

Genus: *Diuraphis* Aizenberg, 1935

Subgenus: *Diuraphis* Aizenberg, 1935

362. *Diuraphis* (*Diuraphis*) *noxia* (Mordvilko ex Kurdjumov 1913)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Subgenus: *Holcaphis* Hille Ris Lambers, 1939

363. *Diuraphis* (*Holcaphis*) *frequens* (Walker, 1848)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Dysaphis* Börner, 1931

Subgenus: *Cotoneasteria* Shaposhnikov, 1964

364. *Dysaphis* (*Cotoneasteria*) *microsiphon* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

Subgenus: *Dysaphis* Börner, 1931

365. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) affinis* (Mordvilko, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

366. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) angelicae* (Koch, 1854)

First record from Iran: [Alikhani et al. \(2010\)](#).

367. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) apiifolia* (Theobald, 1923)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

368. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) brancoi* (Börner, 1950)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

369. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) crataegi* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

370. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) crataegi crataegi* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Radjabi \(1986\)](#).

371. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) devectora* (Walker, 1849)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

372. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) emicis* (Mimeur, 1935)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

373. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) foeniculus* (Theobald, 1923)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

374. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) inulae* (Rezwani, 2008)*

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2008\)](#).

375. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) lappae* (Koch, 1854)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

376. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) lappae cynarae* (Theobald, 1915)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

377. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) lauberti* (Börner, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

378. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) pulverina* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Stroyan \(1970\)](#).

379. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) pulverina iranica* Stroyan, 1970*

First record from Iran: [Stroyan \(1970\)](#).

380. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) radicola* (Mordvilko, 1897)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

381. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) ranunculi* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

382. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) tulipae* (Boyer de Fonscolombe, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

383. *Dysaphis (Dysaphis) vandenboschi* (Stroyan, 1970)

First record from Iran: [Stroyan \(1970\)](#).

Subgenus: *Pomaphis* Börner, 1939

384. *Dysaphis (Pomaphis) aucupariae* (Buckton, 1879)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

385. *Dysaphis (Pomaphis) plantaginea* (Passerini, 1860)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

386. *Dysaphis (Pomaphis) pyri* (Boyer de Fonscolombe, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

387. *Dysaphis (Pomaphis) reaumuri* (Mordvilko, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

388. *Dysaphis (Pomaphis) viennoti* Remaudière, 1989*

First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1989\)](#).

Genus: *Eichinaphis* Narzikulov, 1963

389. *Eichinaphis pamirica* Narzikulov, 1963

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Elatobium* Mordvilko, 1914

390. *Elatobium abietinum* (Walker, 1849)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Ericaphis* Börner, 1939

391. *Ericaphis scammelli* (Mason, 1940)

First record from Iran: [Jalalizand et al. \(2012\)](#).

Genus: Eucarazzia Del Guercio, 1921

392. *Eucarazzia elegans* (Ferrari, 1872)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: Hayhurstia Del Guercio, 1917

393. *Hayhurstia atriplicis* (Linnaeus, 1761)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1981\)](#).

Genus: Hyadaphis Kirkaldy, 1904

394. *Hyadaphis bupleuri* Börner, 1939
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

395. *Hyadaphis coriandri* (Das, 1918)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Mossadegh \(1979\)](#).

396. *Hyadaphis foeniculi* (Passerini, 1860)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

397. *Hyadaphis passerinii* (Del Guercio, 1911)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

398. *Hyadaphis tataricae* (Aizenberg, 1935)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: Hyalopteroides Theobald, 1916

399. *Hyalopteroides humilis* (Walker, 1852)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: Hyperomyzus Börner, 1933**Subgenus: Hyperomyzus Börner, 1933**

400. *Hyperomyzus (Hyperomyzus) lactucae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

401. *Hyperomyzus (Hyperomyzus) pallidus* Hille Ris Lambers, 1935
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Idiopterus Davis, 1909

402. *Idiopterus nephrolepidis* Davis, 1909
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: Iranaphias Remaudière & Davatchi, 1959

403. *Iranaphias dehbandi* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1959*
First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1959a\)](#).

Genus: Liosomaphis Walker, 1868

404. *Liosomaphis atra* Hille Ris Lambers, 1966
First record from Iran: [Mehrparvar \(2016\)](#).

405. *Liosomaphis berberidis* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: Lipaphis Mordvilko, 1928**Subgenus: Lipaphidiella Doncaster, 1954**

406. *Lipaphis (Lipaphidiella) lepidii* (Nevsky, 1929)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Subgenus: Lipaphis Mordvilko, 1928

407. *Lipaphis (Lipaphis) erysimi* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

408. *Lipaphis (Lipaphis) fritzmuelleri* Börner, 1950
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

409. *Lipaphis (Lipaphis) pseudobrassicae* (Davis, 1914)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: Longicaudus van der Goot, 1913

410. *Longicaudus trirhodus* (Walker, 1849)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

411. *Longicaudus trirhodus iranicus* Remaudière, 1993*
First record from Iran: [Remaudière \(1992\)](#).

412. *Longicaudus trirhodus trirhodus* (Walker, 1849)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

Genus: Macrosiphoniella Del Guercio, 1911**Subgenus: Asterobium Hille Ris Lambers, 1938**

413. *Macrosiphoniella (Asterobium) davazhamci* Holman & Szelegiewicz, 1974
First record from Iran: [Kanturski & Barjadze \(2018\)](#).

Subgenus: Macrosiphoniella Del Guercio, 1911

414. *Macrosiphoniella (Macrosiphoniella) abrotani* (Walker, 1852)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).

415. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *absinthii* (Linnaeus, 1758)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).
416. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *aktashica* (Nevsky, 1928)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
417. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *alatafica* (Nevsky, 1928)
First record from Iran: [Hodjad \(1993\)](#).
418. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *artemisiae* (Boyer de Fonscolombe, 1841)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).
419. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *chamaemelifoliae* Remaudière & Leclant, 1972
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
420. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *helichrysi* Remaudière, 1952
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
421. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *kermanensis* Mehrparvar & Rezwani, 2007*
First record from Iran: [Mehrparvar & Rezwani \(2007\)](#).
422. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *millefolii* (De Geer, 1773)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).
423. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *nitida* Börner, 1950
First record from Iran: [Kanturski & Barjadze \(2018\)](#).
424. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *pulvera* (Walker, 1848)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).
425. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *remaudierei* Barbagallo & Nieto Nafria, 2016*
First record from Iran: [Barbagallo & Nafria \(2016\)](#).
426. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *sanborni* (Gillette, 1908)
First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).
427. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *sejuncta* (Walker, 1848)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
428. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *sojaki* Holman & Szelegiewicz, 1974
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
429. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *staegeri* Hille Ris Lambers, 1947
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
430. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *subaequalis* Börner, 1942
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
431. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *subterranea* (Koch, 1855)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).
432. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *tanacetaria* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).
433. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *tapuskae* (Hottes & Frison, 1931)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
Synonym: *Macrosiphoniella chamomillae* Hille Ris Lambers, 1947
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
434. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *usquertensis* Hille Ris Lambers, 1935
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).
435. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Macrosiphoniella*) *vallesiaca* Jörg & Lampel, 1988
First record from Iran: [Mehrparvar \(2017\)](#).
- Subgenus: *Papillomyzus* Szelegiewicz, 1963**
436. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Papillomyzus*) *iranica* Nieto Nafria & Pérez Hidalgo, 2013*
First record from Iran: [Nieto Nafria & Pérez Hidalgo \(2013\)](#).
437. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Papillomyzus*) *papillata* (Holman, 1962)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).
Synonym: *Uroleucon* (*Uroleucon*) *virgatae* (Rezwani & Lampel, 1990)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Lampel \(1990\)](#).
438. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Papillomyzus*) *riedeli* Szelegiewicz, 1963
First record from Iran: [Blackman & Eastop \(2006\)](#).

439. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Papillomyzus*)
tuberculata (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Starý \(1979\)](#).

Synonym: *Uroleucon* (*Lambersius*) *Cousinia*
Lampel & Rezwani, 1993

First record from Iran: [Lampel & Rezwani \(1993\)](#).

440. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Papillomyzus*)
tuberculatumartemiscicola (Bozhko, 1961)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: Phalangomyzus Börner, 1939

441. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Phalangomyzus*)
oblonga (Mordvilko, 1901)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991a\)](#).

Subgenus: Ramitrichophorus Hille Ris Lambers, 1947

442. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Ramitrichophorus*)
medvedevi (Bozhko, 1957)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

443. *Macrosiphoniella* (*Ramitrichophorus*)
nikolajevi Kadyrbekov, 1999

First record from Iran: [Kanturski & Barjadze \(2018\)](#).

Genus: Macrosiphum Passerini, 1860

Subgenus: Macrosiphum Passerini, 1860

444. *Macrosiphum* (*Macrosiphum*)
cholodkovskyi (Mordvilko, 1909)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

445. *Macrosiphum* (*Macrosiphum*) *euphorbiae*
(Thomas, 1878)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

446. *Macrosiphum* (*Macrosiphum*) *funestum*
(Macchiati, 1885)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

447. *Macrosiphum* (*Macrosiphum*) *gei* (Koch, 1855)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

448. *Macrosiphum* (*Macrosiphum*) *rosae*
(Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

449. *Macrosiphum* (*Macrosiphum*) *symphyti*
Barjadze & Chakvetadze, 2008

First record from Iran: [Özdemir & Barjadze \(2015\)](#).

Genus: Megoura Buckton, 1876

450. *Megoura viciae* Buckton, 1876

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Genus: Megourella Hille Ris Lambers, 1949

451. *Megourella purpurea* Hille Ris Lambers,
1949

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: Metopeurum Mordvilko, 1914

452. *Metopeurum fuscoviride* Stroyan, 1950

First record from Iran: [Rajabi-Mazhar et al. \(2008\)](#).

Genus: Metopolophium Mordvilko, 1914

Subgenus: Metopolophium Mordvilko, 1914

453. *Metopolophium* (*Metopolophium*)
dirhodum (Walker, 1849)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1954\)](#).

454. *Metopolophium* (*Metopolophium*) *festucae*
(Theobald, 1917)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Azmayeshfard \(1987\)](#).

Genus: Microlophium Mordvilko, 1914

455. *Microlophium carnosum* (Buckton, 1876)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Synonym: *Microlophium evansi* (Tao, 1963)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

Genus: Myzaphis van der Goot, 1913

456. *Myzaphis oezdemirae* Kanturski &
Barjadze, 2018*

First record from Iran: [Kanturski & Barjadze \(2018\)](#).

457. *Myzaphis rezwanii* Kanturski &
Barjadze, 2018*

First record from Iran: [Kanturski et al. \(2018\)](#).

458. *Myzaphis rosarum* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Myzus Passerini, 1860

Subgenus: Myzus Passerini, 1860

459. *Myzus* (*Myzus*) *borealis* Ossiannilsson,
1959

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

460. *Myzus (Myzus) cerasi* (Fabricius, 1775)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

461. *Myzus (Myzus) lythri* (Schrank, 1801)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

462. *Myzus (Myzus) ornatus* Laing, 1932
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

463. *Myzus (Myzus) padellus* Hille Ris Lambers & Rogerson, 1946
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: Nectarosiphon Schouteden, 1901

464. *Myzus (Nectarosiphon) beybienkoi* (Narzikulov, 1957)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

465. *Myzus (Nectarosiphon) certus* (Walker, 1849)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

466. *Myzus (Nectarosiphon) dianthicola* Hille Ris Lambers, 1966
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1998\)](#).

467. *Myzus (Nectarosiphon) ligustri* (Mosley, 1841)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

468. *Myzus (Nectarosiphon) persicae* (Sulzer, 1776)
First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1948\)](#).

469. *Myzus (Nectarosiphon) persicae nicotianae* (Blackman, 1987)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Subgenus: Sciamyzus Stroyan, 1954

470. *Myzus (Sciamyzus) ascalonicus* Doncaster, 1946
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

471. *Myzus (Sciamyzus) cymbalariae* Stroyan, 1954
First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: Nasonovia Mordvilko, 1914

Subgenus: Nasonovia Mordvilko, 1914

472. *Nasonovia (Nasonovia) compositellae* (Theobald, 1924)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

473. *Nasonovia (Nasonovia) compositellae nigra* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1931)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

474. *Nasonovia (Nasonovia) ribisnigri* (Mosley, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Nearctaphis Shaposhnikov, 1950

475. *Nearctaphis bakeri* (Cowen, 1895)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: Neomyzus van der Goot, 1915

476. *Neomyzus circumflexum* (Buckton, 1876)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: Neomariaella Szwedo & Osiadacz, 2010

477. *Neomariaella lambersi* (Szelegiewicz, 1961)

First record from Iran: [Starý et al. \(2000\)](#).

Genus: Obtusicauda Soliman, 1927

478. *Obtusicauda dolychosiphon* (Umarov, 1964)

First record from Iran: [Holman & Szelegiewicz \(1979\)](#).

Genus: Ovatus Van Der Goot, 1913

Subgenus: Ovatus Van Der Goot, 1913

479. *Ovatus (Ovatus) crataegarius* (Walker, 1850)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

480. *Ovatus (Ovatus) insitus* (Walker, 1849)

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

481. *Ovatus (Ovatus) mentharius* (van der Goot, 1913)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: Paczoskia Mordvilko, 1914

482. *Paczoskia major* Börner, 1950

First record from Iran: [Goodarzarifar et al. \(2010\)](#).

483. *Paczoskia meridionalis* Holman, 1981
First record from Iran: [Holman \(1981\)](#).

Genus: *Phorodon* Passerini, 1860

Subgenus: *Diphorodon* Börner, 1939

484. *Phorodon (Diphorodon) cannabis* Passerini, 1860
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Subgenus: *Phorodon* Passerini, 1860

485. *Phorodon (Phorodon) humuli* (Schrank, 1801)
First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

Genus: *Pleotrichophorus* Börner, 1930

486. *Pleotrichophorus chrysanthemi* (Theobald, 1920)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

487. *Pleotrichophorus glandulosus* (Kaltenbach, 1846)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

488. *Pleotrichophorus persimilis* Börner, 1950
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Plocamaphis* Oestlund, 1923

489. *Plocamaphis flocculosa* (Weed, 1891)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

490. *Plocamaphis flocculosa goernitzii* Börner, 1940
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Pterocomma* Buckton, 1879

491. *Pterocomma konoii* Hori, 1939
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

492. *Pterocomma pilosum* Buckton, 1879
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

493. *Pterocomma populeum* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1984a\)](#).

Genus: *Rhodobium* Hille Ris Lambers, 1947

494. *Rhodobium porosum* (Sanderson, 1900)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Roepkea* Hille Ris Lambers, 1935

495. *Roepkea marchali* (Börner, 1931)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

Genus: *Semiaphis* van der Goot, 1913

496. *Semiaphis anthrisci* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

497. *Semiaphis dauci* (Fabricius, 1775)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

498. *Semiaphis pimpinellae* (Kaltenbach, 1843)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Parvizi \(1990\)](#).

499. *Semiaphis sphondylii* (Koch, 1854)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2010\)](#).

Genus: *Sitobion* Mordvilko, 1914

Subgenus: *Sitobion* Mordvilko, 1914

500. *Sitobion (Sitobion) avenae* (Fabricius, 1775)
First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1954\)](#).

501. *Sitobion (Sitobion) fragariae* (Walker, 1848)
First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

502. *Sitobion (Sitobion) yakini* (Eastop, 1959)
First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

Genus: *Staegeiriella* Hille Ris Lambers, 1947

503. *Staegeiriella necopinata* (Börner, 1939)
First record from Iran: [Derakhshan Shadmehri \(1994\)](#).

Genus: *Staticobium* Mordvilko, 1914

504. *Staticobium latifoliae* (Bozhko, 1950)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

505. *Staticobium limonii* (Contarini, 1847)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1990\)](#).

Genus: *Titanosiphon* Nevsky, 1928

506. *Titanosiphon artemisiae* (Koch, 1855)
First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

507. *Titanosiphon neoartemisiae* (Takahashi, 1921)
First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Synonym: *Titanosiphon bellicosum* (Nevsky, 1928)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Turanoleucon* Kadyrbekov, 2002

508. *Turanoleucon jashenkoi* Kadyrbekov, 2002

First record from Iran: [Goodarzifar et al. \(2016\)](#).

509. *Turanoleucon mitjaevi* Kadyrbekov, 2002

First record from Iran: [Goodarzifar et al. \(2010\)](#).

Genus: *Uroleucon* Mordvilko, 1914**Subgenus: *Belochilum* Börner, 1932**

510. *Uroleucon (Belochilum) inulae* (Ferrari, 1872)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Ahmadian \(1988\)](#).

Subgenus: *Lambersius* Olive, 1965

511. *Uroleucon (Lambersius) erigeronense* (Thomas, 1878)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Ahmadian \(1988\)](#).

Subgenus: *Uroleucon* Mordvilko, 1914

512. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) achilleae* (Koch, 1855)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

513. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) bielawskii* (Szelegiewicz, 1962)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

514. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) caspicum* Rezwani & Lampel, 1990

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Lampel \(1990\)](#).

515. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) chondrillae* (Nevsky, 1929)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Ahmadian \(1988\)](#).

516. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) cichorii* (Koch, 1855)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

517. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) cirsii* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

518. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) elbursicum* Lampel & Rezwani, 1993*

First record from Iran: [Lampel & Rezwani \(1993\)](#).

519. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) hymenocephali* Rezwani & Lampel, 1987*

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Lampel \(1987\)](#).

520. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) hypochoeridis* (Fabricius, 1779)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

521. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) iranicum* Holman, 1980*

First record from Iran: [Holman \(1980\)](#).

522. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) murale* (Buckton, 1876)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

523. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) ochropus* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1939)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

524. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) picridis* (Fabricius, 1775)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

525. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) pilosellae* (Börner, 1933)

First record from Iran: [Mehrparvar \(2017\)](#).

526. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) sonchi* (Linnaeus, 1767)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).

527. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) tanacetii* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

528. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) teheranense* Nieto Nafria & Pérez Hidalgo, 2013*

First record from Iran: [Nieto Nafria & Pérez Hidalgo \(2013\)](#).

529. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) tortuosissimae* Rezwani & Lampel, 1987*

First record from Iran: [Rezwani & Lampel \(1987\)](#).

530. *Uroleucon (Uroleucon) tussilaginis* (Walker, 1850)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

Subgenus: *Uromelan* Mordvilko, 1914

531. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) acroptilidis* Kadyrbekov, Renxin & Shao, 2002

First record from Iran: [Barahoei et al. \(2012\)](#).

532. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) aeneum* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1939)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

533. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) campanulae* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

534. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) carthami* (Hille Ris Lambers, 1948)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

535. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) compositae* (Theobald, 1915)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1991b\)](#).

536. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) helichrysi* Nieto Nafria & Pérez Hidalgo, 2014*

First record from Iran: [Nieto Nafria & Pérez Hidalgo \(2014\)](#).

537. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) jaceae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(1987\)](#).

538. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) rapunculoidis* (Börner, 1939)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Ahmadian \(1988\)](#).

539. *Uroleucon (Uromelan) taraxaci* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Hodjat & Ahmadian \(1988\)](#).

Genus: *Wahlgreniella* Hille Ris Lambers, 1949

540. *Wahlgreniella nervata* (Gillette, 1908)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2001\)](#).

Subfamily: Lachninae Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854

Tribe: Eulachnini Baker, 1920

Genus: *Cinara* Curtis, 1835

Subgenus: *Cinara* Curtis, 1835

541. *Cinara (Cinara) cedri* Mimeur, 1936

First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).

542. *Cinara (Cinara) costata* (Zetterstedt, 1828)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2004\)](#).

543. *Cinara (Cinara) maghrebica* Mimeur, 1934

First record from Iran: [Mortazavi et al. \(2015\)](#).

544. *Cinara (Cinara) palaestinensis* Hille Ris Lambers, 1948

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2004\)](#).

545. *Cinara (Cinara) piceicola* (Cholodkovsky, 1896)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Synonym: *Cinara (Cinara) cistata* Buckton 1881

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

546. *Cinara (Cinara) pilicornis* (Hartig, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

547. *Cinara (Cinara) pini* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First record from Iran: [Nazemi et al. \(2013\)](#).

548. *Cinara (Cinara) pinihabitans* (Mordvilko, 1895)

First record from Iran: [Heidari Latibari et al. \(2016\)](#).

549. *Cinara (Cinara) pruinosa* (Hartig, 1841)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2004\)](#).

Subgenus: *Cupressobium* Börner, 1940

550. *Cinara (Cupressobium) cupressi* (Buckton, 1881)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

Synonym: *Cinara juniperinus* Mordvilko, 1895

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

551. *Cinara (Cupressobium) tujafilina* (Del Guercio, 1909)

First record from Iran: [Eastop & Hodjat \(1980\)](#).

Genus: *Eulachmus* Del Guercio, 1909

552. *Eulachmus agilis* (Kaltenbach, 1843)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

553. *Eulachmus nigricola* (Pašek, 1953)

First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).

554. *Eulachmus rileyi* (Williams, 1911)

First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).

555. *Eulachmus tuberculostemmatum* (Theobald, 1915)

First record from Iran: [Davatchi \(1958\)](#).

Tribe: Lachnini Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854

Genus: *Lachnus* Burmeister, 1835556. *Lachnus roboris* (Linnaeus, 1758)First record from Iran: [Abaii \(1984\)](#).557. *Lachnus swirskii* Hille Ris Lambers, 1954First record from Iran: [Davatchi et al. \(1957\)](#).558. *Lachnus swirskii persicae* Davatchi, Hille Ris Lambers & Remaudiere, 1957*First record from Iran: [Davatchi et al. \(1957\)](#).**Genus: *Pterochloroides* Mordvilko, 1914**559. *Pterochloroides persicae* (Cholodkovsky, 1899)First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).**Tribe: Tramini Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854****Genus: *Protrama* Baker, 1920**560. *Protrama flavescens* (Koch, 1857)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).561. *Protrama radialis* (Kaltenbach, 1843)First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).**Genus: *Trama* von Heyden, 1837****Subgenus: *Neotrama* Baker, 1920**562. *Trama (Neotrama) caudata* Del Guercio, 1909First record from Iran: [Derakhshan Shadmehri \(1994\)](#).**Subgenus: *Trama* von Heyden, 1837**563. *Trama (Trama) rara* Mordvilko, 1908First record from Iran: [Rezwani \(2001\)](#).564. *Trama (Trama) troglodytes* von Heyden, 1837First record from Iran: [Rezwani et al. \(1994\)](#).**Tribe: Tuberolachnini Oestlund, 1942****Genus: *Pyrolachnus* Basu & Hille Ris Lambers, 1968**565. *Pyrolachnus pyri* (Buckton, 1899)First record from Iran: [Hodjat \(1993\)](#).**Genus: *Tuberolachnus* Mordvilko, 1909****Subgenus: *Tuberolachnus* Mordvilko, 1909**566. *Tuberolachnus (Tuberolachnus) salignus* (Gmelin, 1790)First record from Iran: [Farahbakhsh \(1961\)](#).**Subfamily: Macropodaphidinae Zachvatkin & Aizenberg, 1960****Genus: *Macropodaphis* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1958**Synonym: *Macropoda* (Mehrparvar, 2017)567. *Macropodaphis rechingeri* Remaudière & Davatchi, 1958First record from Iran: [Remaudière & Davatchi \(1958\)](#).**Discussion**

The known world fauna of aphids (Aphidomorpha) comprises more than 5500 valid species, which are placed into 712 genera ([Favret, 2019](#)). Considering the number of species in the current checklist about 10% aphid species being known from Iran. Comparing to neighbor countries the number of aphid species is nearly the same as in Turkey ([Akyürek et al., 2019](#)) i.e. 543 and 555 species for Iran and Turkey respectively. However, due to political unrest in most of the other neighboring countries there are not enough studies in this area. Despite this, aphid fauna of Iran is not well investigated yet, if we take into account high floral and landscape diversities of this big country.

According to [Blackman & Eastop \(2019\)](#) about 50% of the aphid species spend all or part of their life feeding on tree. This is also true for Iranian fauna (see [Rezwani, 2004; 2010](#)). Aphids are merely associated with living plants and are among the most destructive insects in the world. In addition to sucking sap of the plant, they act as vectors for various plant viruses ([Goggin, 2007](#)). The pest aphids status in Iran has been well documented ([Rezwani, 2001](#)). However there is no a comprehensive checklist of this insects in Iran before this study. In contrast there are several checklists for other insect groups in this country particularly in recent years ([Paknia et al., 2008; Talebi et al., 2011; Mozaffarian & Wilson, 2011; Moghadam, 2013; Minaei, 2013; Barahoei et al., 2014; Pakarpour et al., 2015](#)).

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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چک لیست شته‌های ایران (Hemiptera: Stenorrhyncha: Aphidomorpha)

فاطمه مؤمنی شهرکی^۱، کامبیز مینایی^{۱*} و شالوا بارجاذزه^۲

۱ بخش گیاهپزشکی، دانشکده کشاورزی، دانشگاه شیراز، ایران.

۲ مؤسسه جانورشناسی، دانشگاه ایالتی ایلینا، تفلیس، گرجستان.

* پست الکترونیکی نویسنده مسئول مکاتبه: *kminaei@gmail.com*

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واژگان کلیدی: شته‌ها، ایران، چک لیست